

Effect of principal instructional leadership on teacher commitment

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ABSTRACT

A comprehensive examination of the impact of instructional leadership provided by school principals on teacher commitment was carried out across different nations, including Indonesia. This research employed a literature review approach, scrutinizing journal articles that delved into the connection between the instructional leadership of school principals and teacher commitment. After applying predefined criteria to 120 chosen articles in this domain, only 15 articles met the specified criteria and were subsequently incorporated into the review. The findings of the literature review revealed that the instructional leadership of school principals and the resulting organizational commitment have a positive, and mostly said statistically significant, effect on teacher organizational commitment in various countries.

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1. INTRODUCTION

National education is a very strategic element in realizing developed and developing countries. Quality education can produce quality and productive human resources [1]. Various aspects are needed to produce quality education, such as government policies, education management, human resources, and management of education funds [2]. Therefore, the government and society jointly realize this mandate through various efforts to develop high-quality education [3]. To fulfill its constitutional duty, the government is compelled to establish a robust and authoritative national educational framework aimed at equipping every Indonesian citizen [4] with the knowledge and skills required to develop into intelligent and competent individuals, grounded in faith, devotion, and exemplary moral values, who are capable of addressing various challenges [5]. A high-quality educational system will yield skilled human capital to facilitate the pursuit of a progressively sophisticated and prosperous society [6].

Teachers as one of the human resources play an important role in the educational process. Teachers are the most important part of the learning process, both formal and non-formal education. Therefore, teachers play an important role in carrying out education in schools so that it runs effectively, efficiently, and productively to achieve the desired goals [7], [8]. The teacher's main task is to teach and be responsible for the implementation of the learning process [9]. Therefore, the welfare of teachers must be considered and not ignored. Teachers must be capable of carrying out their duties so that all work can be completed properly. This requires teachers to be committed, particularly to school organization. Commitment is shown by a strong attitude of belief and acceptance of the duties and obligations assigned to them [10]. The quality of a teacher's teaching performance is best achieved with a high level of commitment. A dedicated teacher not

only teaches their class professionally but also sticks to their skills. Based on the research, it is found that teachers who are dedicated to their professional duties improve their skills through workshops and training activities, continue their education to a higher level, manage their rank, work hard, work thoroughly, and work with integrity [11].

To measure teacher commitment, researchers have identified different types of commitment and have used the appropriate measures of teacher commitment, for example, that adopted from Park [12], Thien and Razak [13], Ware and Kitsantas [14] consisting of three main components: i) commitment to the school organization as shown by the beliefs and practices of teachers to achieve school goals and values, and a willingness to remain employed, ii) commitment to the teaching profession through teacher beliefs and practices for further professional growth, and iii) commitment to students through teacher beliefs and practices to encourage student-oriented teaching. Based on these components, organizational commitment is an important element in developing organizations, including educational organizations, namely schools.

Teacher commitment grows and is influenced by several factors, one of which is the leadership of the school principal [15]. This is confirmed by Flippo [16] and Chen *et al.* [17], who conclude that leadership has a direct impact on employee commitment to the organization. Leadership involvement can also be influenced by individual external factors, organizational culture, organizational climate, job satisfaction, leadership, and teamwork [18], [19]. Principal leadership is one of the factors that influence teacher commitment. Teachers will need encouragement, enthusiasm, guidance, and direction from leaders in completing their work [20]. Principals have different leadership styles, one of which is the instructional leadership style.

Principal instructional leadership plays a pivotal role in fostering collaboration among educators, thereby motivating teachers to invest their efforts in the betterment of their schools [21], [22]. Furthermore, the extent to which principals respect and value teachers, support their professional growth, and promote peer collaboration significantly impacts teachers' dedication to their roles [23], [24]. The leadership actions and disposition of effective principals, as well as their inclination to involve teachers in decision-making processes, significantly shape teachers' perceptions of their educational institutions. These behaviors engender a higher level of commitment among teachers towards their responsibilities and their eagerness to contribute to the progress of the school [25], [26]. As evident from the discussion, the interplay of instructional leadership and commitment holds substantial importance in advancing school effectiveness, elevating student achievements, and enhancing teacher performance. This synergy is achieved through the instructional leadership exhibited by the principal and the commitment demonstrated by teachers towards their educational institutions [27], [28].

The study under consideration delves into various leadership styles proposed by different researchers. However, the author's primary focus lies on the theory of instructional leadership. Within this framework, the principal's role as an instructional leader is to ensure that the learning environment remains consistent, heavily concentrated on educational objectives, practical, and attainable. While implementing instructional leadership is undoubtedly challenging, it is not an unattainable endeavor. This particular leadership style has the potential to significantly enhance a teacher's dedication to their profession. Consequently, this literature review aims to conduct a more comprehensive exploration of the impact of instructional leadership on teacher commitment within educational institutions. The objective is to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on instructional leadership theory in educational settings. Furthermore, this study may serve as a catalyst for further empirical research, particularly in Indonesia, specifically within the region of Lampung. This is particularly crucial as prior research in this area has primarily focused on foreign educational institutions. It is worth noting that there is a scarcity of studies in Indonesia, and specifically within Lampung, that examine the relationship between instructional leadership and teacher commitment. Therefore, the researchers involved in this study are highly motivated to address this research gap.

2. METHOD

The method used in this research is a literature review. The information collected is the basic theory related to the material under study. The data reference sources used in this research is articles. The data sources were selected based on the suitability of the research content with the research topic, the quality of the article, and the year of publication, namely 2016 to 2023. The article analysis process began with a search for articles in international journals through Google Scholar using the keywords "school principal's instructional leadership", and " teacher commitment". The criteria for the articles in this study were as follows: i) published as journal articles, ii) articles using English, iii) focused on the instructional leadership of school principals, iv) discussed teacher commitment, v) contained empirical research, and vi) research using both quantitative and qualitative methods.

After reviewing the literature, the researcher was able to collect 410 using the keywords “principal instructional leadership”, and “teacher commitment”, with the Booleans AND and OR. Then screening was carried out and 120 articles that met the requirements, there were only 15 specific and systematic articles that described the principal's instructional leadership regarding teacher commitment. Furthermore, the stages in the literature search can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of eview procedure

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This literature review focuses on the relationship between instructional leadership and organizational commitment. As such, there are 15 articles analyzed in this paper. The 15 articles reported the main findings of the reviewed articles. The analysis showed that most of the articles focused on increasing organizational commitment through instructional leadership. Most importantly, the subjects of the articles are mostly teachers or students in Asian countries and European countries. The reviewed articles are listed in Table 1 (see Appendix). Table 1 is described and discussed in the following sections.

3.1. Instructional leadership literature

This section reports the main findings from the principal instructional leadership literature. The articles that have been reviewed are the results of research conducted in several Asian and European countries. The distribution of research related to instructional leadership includes Pakistan, Turkey, Indonesia, Malaysia, Iran, China and Oman. Based on the reviewed articles, the method of collecting instructional leadership data uses a quantitative approach. This shows that this context cannot be generalized to other contexts. In addition, the use of questionnaires differs from one article to another, one of which was the questionnaire developed by Hallinger [24], and Sarikaya and Cetin [29]. However, the most commonly used is the Instructional Leadership Questionnaire developed by Hallinger. Therefore, there is a need for more studies on the instructional leadership of school principals which are carried out using the literature review method. This can contribute richer insights into the discussion and can contribute to various educational practices.

3.2. Teacher commitment literature

This section reports the main findings from the teacher commitment literature. The articles that have been reviewed are the results of research conducted in several Asian and European countries. A wide range of research related to organizational commitment includes several countries such as Pakistan, Turkey, Indonesia, Malaysia, Iran, Tanzania, and Oman. Based on the articles reviewed, organizational commitment data collection methods use quantitative and qualitative approaches. Meanwhile, to collect data on organizational commitment, the questionnaire used was developed by Allen and Meyer, Balay, and Wasti [30]–[32]. Allen and Meyer’s questionnaire was the most commonly used to collect organizational commitment data [30].

In the comprehensive review of the literature, the collective objective of the research articles under scrutiny was to assess the impact and correlation between a principal's instructional leadership and teacher commitment, both through direct and indirect means, as well as to predict the extent to which this leadership style influences teacher commitment. Notably, certain studies also delved into the examination of how a principal's instructional leadership affects teacher commitment by considering intervening variables. For instance, Niemted's [37] investigation explored the direct and indirect consequences of a principal's instructional leadership on teacher commitment, utilizing factors like teacher self-efficacy and collective teacher efficacy. The findings from this study highlight the pivotal roles played by teacher self-efficacy and collective teacher efficacy in realizing the impact of school principals' instructional leadership practices in fostering teacher commitment. Consequently, it becomes evident that instructional leadership can be influenced by various other variables. The ensuing section will delve deeper into how instructional leadership shapes teacher commitment.

3.3. The impact of instructional leadership on teacher dedication

The majority of the results of the review of the articles indicate that there is a positive and medium effect of principal instructional leadership on teacher commitment, across the various instruments used. For example, the results of research using the instructional leadership instrument developed by Philip Hellinger and teacher commitment developed by Allen and Mayer were that the variables had a positive relationship at a moderate level [33], [35], [38], [43]. According to research findings, principals should apply intelligence in instructional leadership skills to strengthen teachers' organizational commitment. A leader in education is responsible for carrying out supervisory duties to increase teacher commitment to advancing learning. Therefore, principals must practice broad instructional leadership for teachers' commitment to schools or organizations.

Kiral and Suçiçeği utilized the instruments of their creation [34]. Their study employed Sarikaya and Cetin's leadership instrument [29] and Balay's Commitment instrument [31]. The results of the correlation analysis demonstrated a negative association between the sub-dimensions of instructional leadership and the compliance aspect of organizational commitment. Conversely, a positive correlation was observed between the sub-dimensions of instructional leadership and the identification and internalization dimensions. As a result, school principals must coordinate social activities that facilitate interaction among teachers, students, and various stakeholders. This engagement is essential in garnering support from parents and other parties to enhance the school's success and foster increased organizational commitment among teachers.

Moreover, the findings from a study conducted by Cansoy *et al.* [21] utilized the instructional leadership research tool created by Sarikaya and Cetin [29], along with the commitment instrument developed by Wasti [32]. These results reveal that various aspects, such as school development, instructional effectiveness, the establishment of a robust school culture, student achievement, and teacher performance, have a noteworthy and beneficial impact on teacher commitment. It is worth noting that the behavior exhibited by school principals plays a crucial role in fostering teacher commitment and their willingness to address school-related challenges [21].

Studies examining the impact of principals' instructional leadership and teacher organizational commitment have been carried out in both Asian and Western contexts, spanning various educational levels and multiple countries, such as Pakistan, Turkey, Indonesia, and Malaysia. These investigations encompassed elementary schools, junior high schools, senior high schools, and tertiary education. In sum, the research revealed a positive and moderate influence of the principal's instructional leadership on teacher commitment across all education levels. However, there remains a requirement to enhance principals' proficiency in mastering all relevant indicators to augment teacher commitment.

However, almost all research results show that there is a positive and negative relationship between instructional leadership and commitment at various levels of schools and in various countries. The conclusion is that an instructional leader must be able to master indicators and expand instructional knowledge, to increase teacher commitment to school and work. However other factors can affect the level of correlation, namely other variables such as the level of satisfaction, teacher efficacy, school climate, and organizational culture. In short, previous research has made a significant contribution to refining our understanding of instructional leadership on teacher commitment as the two variables (instructional leadership and teacher commitment) that have a positive, and mosy said significant, influence on teaching achievement.

4. CONCLUSION

This literature review was undertaken to investigate the impact of the instructional leadership provided by school principals on teacher commitment. This research draws upon a diverse range of previous studies conducted in various countries worldwide. The findings reveal a positive, mostly said statistically significant, correlation between a principal's instructional leadership and teacher commitment, as assessed through the utilization of different questionnaires. Moreover, the analysis identifies other variables that play a role in influencing teacher commitment. These findings have important implications for those involved in the field of education. They suggest that instructional leaders should enhance their skills in school leadership to effectively bolster teacher commitment within educational institutions.

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APPENDIX

Table 1. Effect of principal instructional leadership on teacher commitment

Source	Purpose	N/school level/country	Result
[33]	To explore the correlation between the implementation of instructional leadership techniques and the level of organizational commitment within a given context.	There are 335 educators employed in senior high schools across Pakistan.	A strong positive correlation exists between the extent of principal leadership and instructional leadership and the level of commitment within an organization.
[29]	To examine the correlation between the leadership provided by school principals in an instructional capacity and the level of commitment demonstrated by teachers.	There are 441 educators employed in senior high schools throughout Turkey.	A strong connection exists between effective school leadership and the commitment of the organization's members.
[34]	To determine the relationship between teachers' perceptions of principals' Instructional Leadership and levels of organizational commitment.	329 teachers/all levels/Turkey.	Positive correlation between principal and instructional leadership organization commitment.
[35]	Examine the impact of instructional leadership by principals on the organizational commitment of junior high school teachers in Surakarta.	264 teachers/junior high schools/Indonesia.	Positive correlation between principal and instructional leadership organization commitment.
[36]	To measure the relationship between principal instructional leadership (PIL) and teacher instructional leadership (TIL), whether TIL mediates the effect between PIL, teacher self-efficacy, and student learning outcomes.	1,365 teachers and 5,000 students/116 all school levels/China.	Principal instructional leadership is significantly related to teacher instructional leadership.
[37]	Analyze how a principal's ability to lead in learning impacts teacher commitment, considering both the direct and indirect effects through teacher self-efficacy and collective teacher efficacy.	339 teachers/elementary schools/Indonesia.	A strong positive relationship exists between the principal's leadership, teacher self-efficacy, and collective teacher efficacy, contributing to organizational commitment.
[38]	Examine the impact and correlation of instructional leadership on a school's organizational commitment.	There are 370 educators in Malaysian senior high schools.	A strong connection exists between the commitment of an organization and the leadership qualities demonstrated by its principal in the context of instruction.
[21]	To investigate the connection between the instructional leadership actions of school principals, the collective efficacy, and teacher efficacy, alongside teacher organizational commitment.	Educators across all educational levels in Turkey.	A strong connection exists in academic research between effective school leadership (both in terms of administration and teaching) and the commitment of the organization.
[39]	To evaluate the impact of principals' instructional leadership methods on teachers' dedication to the organization.	250 educators in Indonesian high schools.	Principals' instructional leadership is highly beneficial for fostering teachers' dedication to their school and is a practical approach to enhancing their professional growth.
[40]	The influence of instructional leadership practices by principals on the effectiveness of secondary school teachers in the North Central Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.	There are 389 educators in Nigerian high schools.	Strong and positive connections exist between effective school leadership, which encompasses both principal and instructional leadership, and the creation of a favorable learning environment. These connections also significantly and positively impact teachers' overall effectiveness.
[41]	To investigate the interconnection among instructional leadership, the organizational climate, teacher commitment, and job satisfaction.	There are 155 primary school teachers in Indonesia.	Examine the interconnections between instructional leadership, organizational climate, teacher commitment, and job satisfaction, both directly and indirectly.
[42]	To examine the impact of interpersonal leadership (IL) on the performance and dedication of educators.	12 Pakistani universities.	A notable distinction exists in the impact of instructional leadership on teachers' performance and their job commitment.
[23]	To explore the correlation between the instructional leadership of principals, the collective efficacy of teachers, and teacher commitment.	In Iran, there are 121 principals and 886 primary school teachers.	There is a strong and beneficial connection between principal and instructional leadership, along with teacher dedication.
[43]	To investigate the correlation among principal self-confidence, instructional leadership, collective teacher confidence, and teacher commitment to the organization.	In Iran, there are 111 principals and 345 teachers in primary schools.	The SEM findings revealed strong, positive, and statistically significant associations between the variables.
[44]	Examine how school principals' instructional leadership practices influence teachers' utilization of 21st-century teaching and facilitation methods.	243 educators in Malaysian high schools.	"Establishing a strong connection between the instructional leadership practices of school principals and the adoption of 21st-century teaching and facilitation methods by teachers in schools."

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